

The management of information and knowledge flows in Urban Living Labs: a constructivist approach

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Abstract

Though knowledge management has consolidated as a field of study since a long time, the phenomenon has been approached in the context of formal organizations, mainly. In open innovation ecosystems like Urban Living Labs, the creation and dissemination of knowledge is a key issue, that nevertheless should not be approached with such restrictive conceptual approaches as the traditional dichotomy of tacit/explicit knowledge or quantitative designs exclusively focused on technological aspects. In this paper we introduce a work-in-progress of a constructivist, interpretive multiple case study that aims to build an in-depth, comprehensive explanation on the management of information and knowledge flows in the context of Urban Living Labs.

Keywords: *Urban Living Labs; Open innovation; Knowledge management; Knowledge flows; Innovation clusters; Innovation networks*

1 Introduction

How do Urban Living Labs (ULLs) manage the creation and diffusion of knowledge? This is the central question posed by the research that we are currently developing. This paper presents a general overview of the state of progress of our study, as well as a summary of the state of the art, the research objectives and an abridged presentation of the theoretical-methodological framework.

Open innovation ecosystems -like Living Labs, Urban Labs, Fab Labs, or Maker Spaces, among others- proliferate in cities, especially in urban areas with a concentration of population and problems of coexistence and/or sustainability: 'Growing urbanization puts pressure on both social and ecological systems' (Baccarne, Logghe, Schuurman, & Marez, 2016), boosting citizens and institutions to search for creative solutions, based on cooperation between various actors with different skills, competences and resources.

Living Labs can be conceived as ecosystems of third parties (Almirall, Lee, & Majchrzak, 2014), aiming to implement open innovation (Kerry & Danson, 2016; Leminen, Westerlund, & Nyström, 2012; Leydesdorff & Ivanova, 2016) at an urban scale. Social actors involved in knowledge creation are thus ready to 'meet and interact to catalise creativity, trigger invention, and accelerate innovation across scientific and technological disciplines, public and private sectors (...), in a top-down, policy-driven as well as bottom-up, entrepreneurship-empowered fashion' (Carayannis & Campbell, 2011, p. 330).

The structuring of these novel urban phenomena, such as the ULLs, is conditioned by multiplicity: there are multiple stakeholders (Alex, 2011), and multiple managerial levels and informational nodes (Carayannis & Formica, 2008b), too. Implied social agents are also multiple and diverse: university, government, industry and civil society converge in the innovation ecosystem, contributing their respective competences and skills to develop 'co-specialized knowledge assets' (Carayannis & Formica, 2008a, p. xvii). In other words, innovation ecosystems are network-centric (Zahra & Nambisan, 2011). Innovative products and processes are developed and tested in urban space, but are replicable and scalable, even to supra-local levels (Leminen, Rajahonka, & Westerlund, 2017). This latter statement points to some further features of innovation ecosystems: they are solution-oriented (Edwards-Schachter, Matti, & Alcántara, 2012) and citizen-centric (Leminen et al., 2017), assigning cities a role as a 'driver' for innovative solutions (Cohen, Almirall, & Chesbrough, 2017) to urban living issues.

The multi-stakeholder partnership involved in the articulation of an innovation ecosystem is the structural characteristic that has driven scholars and managers to adopt the metaphor of a Triple Helix (university-industry-public administration) (Etzkowitz, 2003; Leminen et al., 2012; Leydesdorff & Zawdie, 2010) or Quadruple Helix (Triple Helix, plus civil society) (Carayannis & Campbell, 2009). ULLs represent one of the shapes this Helix can adopt.

Our research focuses on the management of knowledge flows in the frame of ULLs, considered as outstanding expressions of the Triple Helix or Quadruple Helix model of open innovation.

The defining feature of ULLs is the methodology they apply to achieve innovative solutions for real urban living problems (Dell’Era & Landoni, 2014; Scozzi, Bellantuono, & Pontrandolfo, 2017). This methodology, apart from being solution- and user-centred, stands out for using the city as a laboratory (Cohen et al., 2017) to interactively test products, services or processes in real life (Franz, 2015; Hirvonen-Kantola, Ahokangas, Iivari, Heikkilä, & Hentilä, 2015).

The role that information and knowledge flows play in urban labs’ procedures has been identified by more than just a few researchers (Baccarne et al., 2016; Lehmann, Frangioni, & Dubé, 2015; Westerlund & Leminen, 2011). Nevertheless, while theoretical investigation has clearly stated this connection, empirical studies concerning ULLs tend to postpone knowledge flows to a rather secondary position, putting instead more attention to structures and patterns of actors’ interaction inside these complex networks (Georges et al., 2015; Juujärvi & Lund, 2015), or governance and decision-making (Gatta, Marcucci, & Le Pira, 2017; Voytenko, McCormick, Evans, & Schliwa, 2016).

Another key aspect of ULLs is their intensive use of digital Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) (Baccarne, Schuurman, Mechant, & De Marez, 2014). Digital ICT are, in fact, imprinted in ULLs’ mission, management, and operation (Lehmann et al., 2015). Therefore, it would seem a hardly justifiable omission not to consider ICT in an empirical approach to the information and knowledge phenomena that take place within ULLs. Nevertheless, material resources and formal information systems have traditionally received a disproportionate attention in comparison with the social or cultural aspects of the processes of knowledge creation and dissemination in organizations. This impels us to consider the benefits that the application of a qualitative, interpretive and constructivist perspective could bring to the field of knowledge management (Hislop, 2009).

This research project responds to a concern about the management of information and knowledge flows in the context of the complex partnership networks that characterize ULLs. We aim to offer both conceptual and methodological contributions to the field of study. In terms of theoretical and conceptual development, the research aspires to contribute not only to the topic of open innovation, but to the empirical studies of information and knowledge flows, in that it widens the problem to encompass complex networks (i.e., networks that are multi-dimensional, multi-level, and multi-faceted). On the other hand, the methodological contribution would rest in an empirical, inductive, in-depth explanation of the way knowledge is managed inside ULLs.

Two main questions arise from this problem. First, how are information and knowledge flows managed in the framework of an open innovation ecosystem? And second, how does the

complexity of multi-partner networks impact on the management of information and knowledge?

We can consider that there are three factors involved in the problem that motivates this research: 1) The characteristics of the networks of actors and stakeholders that are the pillar of open innovation platforms like ULLs. 2) Information and knowledge flows that contribute to shape those networks, and the correspondent relation between these two phenomena. 3) The management of those flows, which connects with the strategic dimension of open innovation. The three factors previously enumerated give rise to three investigative objectives, respectively.

The first objective consists in describing and categorising the multi-stakeholders network of an urban living lab. As an initial conceptual assumption, we consider that at least two dimensions affect the complexity of these structures. On the one hand, we can identify a territorial or spatial dimension (Canals, Boisot, & MacMillan, 2008), in the sense that open innovation platforms, including ULLs, tend to form innovation nodes (Rickne, Laestadius, & Etzkowitz, 2012), which would presumably have an impact on the production and circulation of information and knowledge. On the other hand, a substantive dimension could be categorized, meaning the affinity of topics or objectives pursued by the different innovation platforms that lead them to constitute virtual networks, even when there is no geographical proximity (Salvador, Mariotti, & Conicella, 2013). We consider that the issue of proximity, whether geographic or thematic, can be better described and analysed with the help of geolocalisation and data visualisation procedures, such as mapping techniques, for example. Therefore, our methodological design includes some quantitative techniques for the analysis and visualisation of networks and nodes.

The second objective of the research is to explain the information and knowledge flows that take place in ULLs. This goal involves studying how both phenomena (information and knowledge) are interrelated. At this point we see the need to address some recurring concepts, such as tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995). To do so, we renounce the dichotomous perspectives that have usually characterized the field of knowledge management and we lean, instead, toward interpretive (Hislop, 2009) and non-incremental approaches (M. Boisot & Canals, 2004).

Finally, the third objective proposes to explain the decision-making processes involved in the production and diffusion of knowledge in ULLs. This interest brings us to the problem of the governance of innovation and knowledge (Bahlmann & Huysman, 2008; Bocquet & Mothe, 2010; Bulkeley et al., 2016), which involves strategic considerations about the management of material resources (including technology, for example) and symbolic resources (like human capital) and their impact on knowledge management.

2 State of the Art

Knowledge management has consolidated as a discipline with multiple and interdisciplinary intellectual sources (Davenport & Prusak, 1998). Nevertheless, the study of knowledge flows and the strategies, resources and procedures applied to manage them has been more frequently approached in relation to formal and stable organizations. Unlike more traditional organizations or corporations, ULLs can present different shapes depending on their objectives or functions. Unlike more traditional organizations or corporations, ULLs can present different shapes depending on their objectives or functions. They can rest on temporary networks or stable organizations, with a structured org chart; they can consist in an isolated project or a long-lasting strategy or policy. Regardless, they constitute multi-dimensional, multi-partner and dynamic networks, according to most authors (Baccarne et al., 2016; Leminen, 2015).

In their classic work, Nonaka and Takeuchi (1996) described the connection between information flows and knowledge and, besides, highlighted the relevance of knowledge management for organizations. In the field of organizational studies, knowledge management has consolidated as a discipline for quite a long time (Davenport & Prusak, 1998). The academic interest towards knowledge flows has gone beyond organizations boundaries, reaching the level of societal context, especially since the paradigm of knowledge and information society (Castells, 1996) has succeeded and established. Similarly, information and knowledge flows have proved their impact on cities and urban living. This is an underpinning idea at the bottom of i-City theory (Castells, 1989).

The link between knowledge and innovation results outstanding and primordial in organizational contexts (Hislop, 2009; Swan, Newell, Scarbrough, & Hislop, 1999). At innovation urban spaces, however, this link has been established in conceptual terms, mainly (Hirvonen-Kantola et al., 2015; Westerlund & Leminen, 2011). Nonetheless, although a minority, the empirical studies on ULLs also provide important observations on how information and knowledge flows are handled in these urban innovation ecosystems (Schuurman, Mahr, De Marez, & Ballon, 2015; Voytenko et al., 2016).

The topic has served as a conceptual basis for some case studies, such as the work of Scholl and Kemp (Scholl & Kemp, 2016) or Gascó (Gascó, 2017). In these two cases, there is an interest in describing the connection between learning processes and urban governance policies. Gatta, Marcucci and Le Pira (Gatta et al., 2017) also position themselves at the political or strategic level of decision-making. Their study reveals a pragmatic interest, aspiring to modelling a strategy for the integration of new knowledge produced in ULLs within the framework of the most general urban policies.

From a different perspective, more familiar to personal interactions, Ståhlbröst and Holst (2017) have studied the learning processes and the adoption of digital innovation, applying the same case study approach that characterizes the majority of research in ULLs. Also Sharp

and Salter (2017) realize the convenience of approaching the perspective of the users or participants of a Living Lab to understand knowledge processes in these innovation ecosystems. At this same level -the users- Edwards-Schachter, Matti and Alcántara (2012) have studied the effects that the age gap may have on the adoption of business opportunities between different types of participants of a Living Lab. Some research has focused on identifying the factors that can affect the degree of involvement of the participants in an innovation project (Buhr, Federley, & Karlsson, 2016; Sharp & Salter, 2017; Voytenko et al., 2016).

In this sense, we could say that we have two levels in which the creation of "social value" (Baccarne et al., 2014) can be potentially produced from the generation of new knowledge: on the one hand, the level of strategic decisions that affect the collective of the citizens of a determined ecosystem of innovation (that is to say, the level of the policies) and on the other the level of the users and their own learnings. Two levels that should be considered in the definition of the objectives of our own research, as well as in the theoretical-methodological design and in the selection of data collection and analysis procedures.

If we are seeking more specific tools -with greater descriptive potential- to analyse the information and knowledge flows among the partners of ULLs, we can see that there the available analytical models are not many.

Leydesdorff et al. (2014) apply a 'Triple Helix indicator' to assess information exchange among partners in innovation ecosystems. The production of organizational knowledge has been explained in terms of a tacit/explicit relation (Davenport & Prusak, 1998; Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995, 1996) or a process of codification/abstraction/diffusion (M. Boisot & Canals, 2004). These models have been applied and validated in the framework of an organization, but innovation ecosystems like ULLs are multi-dimensional (Drechsler & Natter, 2012; Ståhlbröst & Holst, 2017), multi-level (Lehmann et al., 2015; Leydesdorff & Zawdie, 2010) and multi-faceted (Alavi & Leidner, 2001) networks, which suggests the convenience of reviewing the models of information and knowledge flows.

3 Methodological Design

Most investigations on ULLs apply a conceptual approach (Baccarne, Schuurman, & De Marez, 2015). On the other hand, empirical studies on this subject tend to utilize a qualitative and exploratory case study design (Baccarne et al., 2014; Gascó, 2017).

Wishing to give some continuity to this line of research, along with the aim of furthering the findings about knowledge flows inside ULLs, we choose the multiple case study as our research method. The appropriateness of this empirical approach has been proved along several studies (Baccarne et al., 2015; Bakici, Almirall, & Wareham, 2013; Edwards-Schachter et al., 2012; Scholl & Kemp, 2016). Though admitting that the methodological

limitations of a case study design lie in the fact that results can hardly be extrapolated to a larger sample (Georges et al., 2015), researchers apply this method as a way to illustrate one or a few cases in a real-life context (Baccarne et al., 2015; Bakici et al., 2013; Yin, 2009). As we could observed in the review of the state of the art, researchers have identified at least two levels of the relationship that links ULLs with the subject of the management of knowledge flows: a level linked to policies and decision-making (strategic level) and the level of interactions between individuals or groups (level of action or interaction). The theoretical-methodological design of our multiple case study should approach both levels in some way. Our research proposal aims to advance an interpretive and inductive explanation (Corbin & Strauss, 1996; Miles & Huberman, 1994) of the management of information and knowledge flows inside ULLs. To achieve this purpose, in-depth semi-structured (Eisenhardt, 1989; Gillham, 2001) and multidimensional (Baccarne et al., 2015) case studies will be carried out. Our research design has been inspired, too, by the qualitative methodology of multiple case study developed by Leminen, Rajahonka and Westerlund (2017), and founded upon Yin's approach (Yin, 2009).

Collected data will be analysed through a mixed method, with both qualitative and quantitative techniques (Quivy & Van Capmenhoudt, 1997), including mapping techniques and the application of a location intelligence software to analyse the spatial dimension of knowledge networks and to geo-reference the presence of nodes or clusters of open innovation labs. This quantitative information will serve as the basis for the selection of in-depth case studies. Our research involves several phases, as is usual in case studies. Currently, the research is in an initial stage, in which the main objective is the exploration of the ULLs landscape to build a system of categories that will allow us to define the profiles of the cases that will be analysed in-depth. That is to say that the result of this first phase of the investigation will consist in the definition of the number and type of ULLs that will be included in the analysis. This stage is currently underway and therefore we do not yet have conclusive results, but we can provide some research advances.

4 State of progress

The first phase (exploratory) of our research rests on the basis of the theoretical framework and the state of the art of investigations on knowledge management in innovation systems. This theoretical background reveals the relevance of network participation (Castells, 1989; Cohen et al., 2017) for knowledge management in ULLs.

As a starting point for the exploratory study, we have chosen the Living Labs pertaining to the ENoLL network and located in European Union countries. At this stage, the selection is based on a documentary review of the information published on the official website of the network (<https://enoll.org/network/living-labs/>), exclusively.

This rapid documentary review helps us to verify the relevance of the Quadruple Helix model.

Although it also suggests that the complexity of information and knowledge flows in systems integrated by four types of partners can be quite elevated. It could even be possible that previous models (like TH indicator (Leydesdorff et al., 2014)) that have already been tested to the study of the Triple helix may not be directly applicable.

5 Preliminary results and conclusions

The review of previous studies on the management of knowledge and information in organizations reveals three central points: first, that it consists in a consolidated field; second, that research has privileged descriptive approaches and technical aspects; and third, that the conceptual and methodological framework must undergo some updates when the object of study is no longer a stable organization, such as a firm, but an open innovation platform, such as urban living labs.

Our research, which is still at an early stage, is considered as a multiple in-depth case study of how information and knowledge flows are managed in Urban Living Labs. The project intends to make a theoretical contribution to the field of knowledge management, by connecting this topic with the phenomenon of open innovation. In addition, it seeks to contribute to the methodological field, applying a constructivist and interpretive approach, with a combination of qualitative and quantitative techniques.

After the first steps of the exploratory research, we arrive to the conclusion that the ULLs to be included in the multiple case study (qualitative in-depth research) must meet three fundamental requirements. These requirements result relevant in accordance to the academic literature and the information obtained from the preliminary documentary research (review of the web):

- i) They should be part of a network or cluster of open innovation systems, since this can foreseeably affect the inputs and outputs of information (Bahlmann & Huysman, 2008) and therefore the management of knowledge flows.
- ii) They should have active projects, executed under the methodology of Living Lab, which is characterized by real-life tests of innovative solutions to urban living issues (Steen & Van Bueren, 2017).
- iii) They should respond to the model of Quadruple Helix, that is, present a multi-partner structure, with participants coming from the productive sector, academic institutions, and government institutions (Triple Helix), plus the participation of representatives of civil society (Carayannis & Campbell, 2009).

These criteria will allow us to advance in the definition of the profiles and the number of cases that will be studied in depth in the following phase of investigation.

If we try to make a forecast of the difficulties that we may find in the phase of in-depth study, we can think of the probability of a high degree of complexity of the relations of exchange of

information, since each case will present at least four types of partners (Quadruple Helix). In this way, the application of a model such as the TH Indicator (Leydesdorff et al., 2014) will probably present some difficulties and it would be necessary to adapt it.

On the other hand, we previously pointed out the conceptual interest that a non-incrementalist model (such as Boisot's (1999) model of codification/abstraction/diffusion of information and knowledge) can have; although it is also necessary to recognize the difficulties to take it to the empirical field. But there is an aspect of this model that is especially interesting when it comes to the study of multipartners systems: we refer to the problem of coding and abstraction. These two phenomena are basic issues of the processes of knowledge creation and transfer in an organization. In addition, we can state as an initial theoretical assumption that coding and abstraction will present a high complexity when it comes to a network of collaboration between participants with highly diverse characteristics and objectives, as in the Quadruple Helix model (Campbell & Carayannis, 2010). One aspect that we must add to the operational difficulties of Boisot's model. Even so, the conceptual contributions of this model make it advisable that we take it into account as part of the theoretical framework of the research. For example, we can consider the question of how do an ULL's partners resolve the differences among their respective linguistic codes or ontologies or the conceptual categorizations they utilize.

The nature of the problem here presented leads us to approaching this question from the point of view of the various involved cultures. Therefore, we think that a qualitative methodology, supported by the constructivist perspective, is the appropriate one to address this study.

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